

Does the Workplace Environment Impact on Employee Performance?

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the effect of employees' Environmentally-Friendly, work environment, employee performance, and job satisfaction. The research was carried out during the 2021 Covid-19 pandemic. The research subject was 65 employees who worked at the Bali Design and Business Institute. Inferential evaluation on this examination makes use of the SEM PLS model and is processed with Smart PLS version 3.2.8 to evaluate the research model. The results showed, based on the results of the direct and indirect effects tests, it can be concluded that by testing the direct effects, all the proposed hypotheses can be retained, that is to say that there is a positive influence between respect for the environment of employees on employee performance and job Satisfaction.

Keywords: Work Environment, Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world economic order in various sectors has changed due to the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19). Almost all countries have implemented physical distancing to break the chain of the spread of Covid-19. The Indonesian government itself has also advised its people to carry out activities at home, including work. However, this suggestion cannot be fully implemented by certain industries, including educational institutions in Bali, Indonesia.

As with employees at the Bali Design and Business Institute, due to operational reasons that must provide excellent service (face to face) to students and prospective students, several divisions are required to continue working in the office while continuing to implement health protocols such as maintaining cleanliness, maintaining distance, providing masks and hand sanitizer, maintaining the safety of students, prospective students and therefore, some employees who are still working in the office continue to do their jobs as before with the implementation of shorter working hours.

Non-profit-oriented organizations in dealing with the current business situation cannot waste the performance of their employees because the achievement of organizational goals is largely determined by their performance. Many factors determine the increase in employee performance, one of which is the environmental factor in which they work (Heath, 2006). Employees who feel comfortable with their workplace will also be motivated to maximize productivity if they do, are in the right work environment it will greatly affect their work results? (Chandrasekar, 2011).

Physical work environment and psychosocial work environment are two work environment factors that need to be considered to support employee performance improvement. Chandrasekar (2011) mentions the layout of office equipment, workspace design, and the availability of work facilities are examples of physical work environment factors while working conditions, role suitability, work procedures, work behavior, policies, superior support, subordinate support are some examples of the work environment psychosocial.

Researchers have claimed that environmental problems are mostly caused by human behavior (Daily et al., 2009; Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Their behavior contributes to the preservation and greening of the work environment and has an impact on more environmental pollution. The behavior of saving water use, turning off lights when leaving the workspace, and using work tools which can still be used are forms of green behavior of employees in their work environment

(Abdulgaffar, 2017). Therefore, it is very important to promote the "green behavior" of employees in today's organizations.

Many studies have been carried out by experts regarding the work environment and green behavior of employees in the workplace. Many also believe that work environment factors greatly affect employee job satisfaction (Westerman et al. Yamamura, 2007) and employee performance (Wang and Boubekri, 2010) so an organization needs to pay attention to the working environment of their employees as this will greatly affect well-being, satisfaction and performance (Samani, et.al., 2015)

In this regard, the factor of the work environment during the Covid-19 pandemic needs to be a concern to achieve employee satisfaction and performance. Supporting the workplace with health protocols should make it possible to obtain results for the continuity of services to employees in the world of education.

II. THEORETICAL BREVIEW

Environmentally-friendly behavior

"Going green" has become a growing issue around the world to encourage businesses to keep improving their green capabilities and apply imaginative green ideas to protect the environment and improve business performance. Because of an increase in an adequate understanding of the green problem, now many companies have improved their overall green performance to get a competitive advantage and knowledge about green innovation. Organizational green performance can help companies in developing operational strategies and creating successful green products. Environmental performance has an impact on the regulatory developments of companies, in particular, prevention of pollution and reducing resources and waste, more productive, and green solutions.

In particular, ecological behavior is defined as behavior that minimizes harm to the the environment as possible or even for the benefit of the environment in the future (Steg & Vlek, 2009). The green behavior of employees seeks to further encourage their behavior in terms of recycling, preserving the environment, and reducing waste.

Anne Kane (2012) in her research found that the implementation of the green workplace initiative program is adopt environmentally friendly strategies and ensure that green behavior is embedded in all members of the organization. This global achievement not only brings green organizations, but also smart organizations that can attract quality staff, retain productive staff and create a pleasant work environment

Environmental care behavior should also be exemplified by top leaders and department heads. They play an important role in greening the organization and changing the way employees perceive their environment through sharing values, offering inspiration and motivation, and building strong relationships with employees (Robertson and Barling, 2013).

Workplace Environment

Among the many determinants of the increase in employee satisfaction and performance, the work environment has an important role that requires the attention of the organization. A comfortable working environment can improve employee performance in the organization (Shikdar and Shawaqed, 2003, El-Zeiny, 2013). This shows that when employees work in a comfortable place that supports them physically and psychologically, they will be able to produce optimal performance.

Mohammad (2017) defines the work environment as a place where someone carries out the process of completing the tasks that are their responsibility. An important aspect of the work environment is the physical workplace environment and psychosocial work environment.

The physical work environment can include workspace layout, furniture, work desk layout, lighting, room size, ventilation, air conditioning, lighting, and surrounding sounds. (Cascio, 2000). A psychosocial work environment can include a work environment outside of the physical work environment such as support from superiors, support from colleagues, the work itself, clarity of work rules, clarity of orders, emotional control and work rules. (Samson et al. 2015)

Sedarmayanti, (2003) states that a healthy work environment is the dream of employees. A healthy work environment must be appropriate with conditions in which employees can carry out their work in a comfortable, safe, clean, and ideal way. Here, eligibility is not only understood in the conditions of the physical work environment, but must also be balanced with the psychosocial work environment. Badayai, (2010) mentions an adequate work environment is a critical factor that it not only affects employee performance, but also job satisfaction, social relationships and well-being.

Job Satisfaction

Employee job satisfaction is an important part that should get attention in improving employee performance and organizational performance. Currently, almost all organizations have realized that the physical and mental health of employees must be considered in terms of their work satisfaction to achieve maximum productivity. Monjamed et al., (2004)

Jamil (2016) states that the satisfaction felt by employees is an emotional feeling and the response given to what they are doing. Job satisfaction is defined as a way of satisfying the main professional needs of employees at work with a pleasant feeling (Kazemian, 2005). Meanwhile, Kasim (2017) provides an understanding of job satisfaction as an individual's attitude shown towards the work they do. This attitude can be formed because there is a difference between the results of the compensation they receive and what they expect to receive. So here there will be differences in the level of job satisfaction that will be felt by each employee (Suryani et al, 2019)

Job satisfaction is the main key for an organization to realize its performance. Organizations that do not consider the job satisfaction of their employees tend not to be able to achieve maximum performance. If employees have high motivation, satisfaction, and enthusiasm, they will exert all their skills towards organizational goals because this involves the psychological atmosphere of pleasant or unpleasant feelings about their work (Smith et al, 2007).

Employee Performance

The achievement of organizational goals cannot be separated from the performance of their employees which describes how these employees do their jobs for the achievement of business success and profitability. In general, employee performance refers to the level of how well a person performs in completing his work (Suryani et al, 2017).

Employee performance is the achievement of work goals including employee work processes and achievements that can be measured Armstrong (2006). Performance is defined as the work of a person or group of people in the organization (Frese and Sonnentag, 2001). Employee performance is needed in organizations, high-performing employees will quickly meet organizational goals. Platt and Sobotka (2010) define employee performance as the combined result of the efforts, abilities, and perceptions of employees in completing their tasks. Employee performance here can be assessed from the results of their work and behavioral changes made when employees work.

Many factors can affect the improvement of employee performance in the organization including job satisfaction (Monjamed et al., 2004) and work environment, both physical environment and psychosocial work environment (Stup, 2003). Employees who are satisfied with their work and comfortable in their work environment will be able to improve their performance.

III. HYPOTHESIS

Workplace Environment to Job Satisfaction

The impact of physical and psychosocial working conditions on employees' job satisfaction has been widely studied. In his study on the psychosocial environment, Srivastava (2008) found that it has a positive and significant effect on increasing employees' job satisfaction. The psychosocial environment investigated, such as management support, employee benefits, and interpersonal relationships, influences the behavior of employees, which in turn affects their performance and the effectiveness of the organization.

A comfortable work environment can stimulate increased performance and employee satisfaction (Luthans et al., 2008). This environment can include providing support from superiors, co-workers, and other divisions that can make them feel comfortable doing their jobs. Westerman and Yamamura, (2007) in their research found that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. The same results were obtained with Lee and Brand (2005), which states that employees who are satisfied with their physical working environment are more likely to do a better job and achieve better results.

The physical work environment in the form of workspace arrangement was found to have a significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction. Research conducted in the hospital industry by Clarke et al., (2001) found a low work environment had a significant effect on the level of staff fatigue and employee dissatisfaction with their work. Similar results were also found by Breau and Rhéaume (2014) in their research in hospitals found a positive and significant relationship between the work environment and employee job satisfaction. The results of the study indicate that the

creation of a positive and comfortable work environment affects the increase in job satisfaction among hospital nurses, especially in the emergency room.

Based on the outcomes of this study, speculation may be drawn from this study

H1: The work environment has a significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction

Workplace Environment to Employee Performance

The work environment is one of the important components in achieving organizational performance through improving the performance of their employees. An adequate work environment greatly influences employee performance, especially in completing their tasks. Employee performance is very broad in terms of reducing errors in completing work, increasing work innovation, increasing teamwork, and decreasing the absence and retention of employees (Al-Anzi, 2009).

In several studies that have been conducted, the work environment, both physical and psychosocial work environments, was found to affect employee performance. Hamed (2009) in his study in the banking sector found that a comfortable office design with a supportive interior was found to affect the level of employee motivation and increase their overall performance. Room layout, lighting, sound, and adequate ventilation were also found to have a positive and significant effect on increasing employee productivity and performance. (Ajala, 2012), The same result was also found in a study conducted by Al-Omari and Okasheh (2017).

Psychosocial factors in the work environment can also impact employees' workplace emotions, which can affect their work attitudes. Chandrasekar (2011) mentions that non-cognitive factors affect a person's ability to face work pressures which can lead to a decrease in productivity at the workplace.

No less important is workplace safety, a quiet workspace, the arrangement of the availability of informal and formal meeting areas, the physical location of the workplace such as furniture, noise, lighting, temperature, air quality in the workplace, personal storage areas, and others that have an impact on employee performance. because a good and comfortable work environment usually increases employee performance, and if the work environment is not adequate it can risk reducing employee performance. The overall work environment was found to have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and employee performance at the hospital (Ramli, 2019)

Based on the results of this study, a hypothesis can be drawn:

H2: The work environment has a significant positive effect on employee performance

Job Satisfaction to Job Performance

Every enterprise must take note of the job satisfaction and performance in their employees and keep to degree this phenomenon for the success of organizational overall performance through thinking about that process pleasure has an effect on employee performance in addition to on work efficiency, work quality, and employee retention (Monjamed, et al., 2004). Job satisfaction is considered an important factor contributing to success at work and leading to higher levels of performance and personal satisfaction. Moazen (2011) in his research on the education sector found that job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance and also affects the teaching quality of their teachers.

Yperen (2003) mentions a positive attitude and satisfaction of employees will increase their awareness of working efficiently and contribute to the effectiveness of their work. This is in line with the research conducted. Maulana et al., (2013) found the satisfaction felt by employees had a positive and significant influence on their performance.

Kargan et al., (2011) found that job satisfaction plays an important role in improving employee performance and organizational performance. Employees who are dissatisfied with their work will not be able to contribute effectively to work. Hadizadeh (2014) in his research also found a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs are found to improve the quality of performance better. A positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance was also found by Mirmolae et al., (2005) and Monjamed et al., (2004).

Based on the results of this study, the following hypotheses can be drawn:

H3: job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

Research Model

Based on the theoretical description, a research model was built, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

Population and Sample

This research was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021. Research Objects are employees who work at the Bali Institute of Design and Business. Respondents in this study were employees who were still working in the office during Covid-19, totaling 65 employees of the Bali Design and Business Institute who were appointed as research objects. The number of 65 people is used entirely as a saturated sample

Data Collection and Testing

The data collection of this research was carried out through the distribution of questionnaires and the testing of the research instrument was analyzed using SEM PLS. The focus of the researched variable is Employee' environmentally-friendly behavior tested with 3 items questions referring to Abdul Ghaffar, (2017), Workplace Environment was tested with 6 question items referring to Nanzushi (2015) and Samson et al., (2015), Job Satisfaction was tested with 3 question items referring to Kwak et al., (2019) and Employee Performance was tested with 3 question items referring to onUğur Yozgat et al., (2013)

Table 1: Research variable

Variable	Items	Source
Employees' environmentally-friendly behavior	I turn off the light when I leave the room	Abdulghaffar, (2017)
	I report if there is a water faucet leak	
	I use office equipment that can still be used	
Workplace Environment	I have a comfortable workspace	Nanzushi (2015) Samson et al., (2015)
	I have adequate work tools	
	I am happy with my workplace	
	My coworkers support my work	
	My boss always helps when there are work problems	
	I received clear job details	
Job Satisfaction	I am satisfied with the compensation I received	Kwak et al., (2019)
	I am satisfied with the bonus rewards provided by the company	
	I am satisfied with the promotion provided	
Employee Performance	I can achieve the given work target	Uğur Yozgat et al., (2013)
	I can complete assignments on time	
	I have a little error in completing the task	

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data analysis

The data collection of this research was carried out through the distribution of questionnaires and the testing of the research instrument was analyzed using SEM PLS.

The focus of the researched variable is Employee' environmentally-friendly behavior tested with 3 items questions referring to Abdul Ghaffar, (2017), Workplace Environment was tested with 6 question items referring to Nanzushi (2015) and Samson et al., (2015), Job Satisfaction was tested with 3 question items referring to Kwak et al., (2019) and Employee Performance was tested with 3 question items referring to onUğur Yozgat et al., (2013).

Assessing the Outer Model

There are 3 standards withinside the use of facts evaluation strategies with SmartPLS to evaluate the outer model, specifically convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability. and Reliability – Alpha (α) Cronbach:

1. Convergent validity is used to validate the variable indicator in terms of load factor value. This value will be accepted if the loading factor value is above 0.7, for the initial stage of developing a measurement scale the loading value of 0.50 to 0.60 is considered sufficient (Chin, 1998 in Ghozali & Latan, 2015:74). However, the loading factor value that ranges from 0.5 to 0.6 will be completely removed if it can increase the AVE value it has, which must be above 0.5 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015: 74). Table 2 shows the loading factor value of each indicator. It can be observed that some indicators have a loading factor below 0.5 which will be removed immediately to increase the AVE of the research model

Table 2: First Outer Loading Results

	Employee Performance	Employee' Environmentally - Friendly Behavior	Job Satisfaction	Workplace Environment
X1.1		-0.035		
X1.2		0.785		
X1.3		0.868		
X2.1				-0.064
X2.2				0.7
X2.3				0.819
X2.4				0.871
X2.5				0.798
X2.6				0.798
Y1.1			0.819	
Y1.2			0.755	
Y1.3			0.832	
Y2.1	0.876			
Y2.2	0.745			
Y2.3	0.795			

Indicators whose values are invalid or less than 0.5 must be removed from the model, so for X1.1 and X2.1 indicator models, they must be removed, and then the PLS algorithm is repeated and the results can be seen in Table 3 which shows all indicators more than 0, 5. Furthermore, the examination of convergent validity is by looking at the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. The indicator is taken into consideration to have precise convergent validity if it has an AVE cost of greater than 0.5 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015:74), the results can be seen in Table 4.

Table 3: Second Outer Loading Results

	Employee Performance	Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior	Job Satisfaction	Workplace Environment
X1.2		0.785		
X1.3		0.868		
X2.2				0.701
X2.3				0.819
X2.4				0.871
X2.5				0.798
X2.6				0.798
Y1.1			0.819	
Y1.2			0.755	
Y1.3			0.832	
Y2.1	0.876			
Y2.2	0.744			
Y2.3	0.795			

Table 4: Results AVE

	Average Variance Extracted(AVE)
Employee Performance	0.651
Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior	0.685
Job Satisfaction	0.644
Workplace Environment	0.639

The AVE value above shows that all variables have an AVE value of more than 0.5. Next look at the value of Cronbach's Alpha. Constructs are declared reliable if the value of Cronbach's alpha is above 0.7 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015: 76-77). The results of the composite reliability test are in Table 5

Table 5: Initial Cronbach's Alpha Results

	Cronbach's Alpha
Employee Performance	0.733
Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior	0.544
Job Satisfaction	0.728
Workplace Environment	0.857

The Cronbach's Alpha value above shows the variable Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior does not meet the requirements (> 0.7), therefore the X1.2 indicator on the variable Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior which has The lowest Outer Loading value of 0.785 was removed from the model, the results can be seen in Table 6. The AVE value can be seen in Table 7 for all variables above 0.5. Cronbach's Alpha value can be seen in Table 8 for all variables above 0.7.

Table 6: Third Outer Loading Results

	<i>Employee Performance</i>	<i>Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior</i>	<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	<i>Workplace Environment</i>
X1.3		1,000		
X2.2				0.698
X2.3				0.821
X2.4				0.871
X2.5				0.798
X2.6				0.799
Y1.1			0.807	
Y1.2			0.732	
Y1.3			0855	
Y2.1	0.882			
Y2.2	0.753			
Y2.3	0.782			

Table 7: ResultsFinal AVE

	Average Variance Extracted(AVE)
<i>Employee Performance</i>	0.652
<i>Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior</i>	1,000
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	0.639
<i>Workplace Environment</i>	0.639

Table 8: Final Cronbach's Alpha Results

	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Employee Performance</i>	0.733
<i>Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior</i>	1,000
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	0.728
<i>Workplace Environment</i>	0.857

2. Discriminant validity is finished to make certain that every idea of every latent variable isn't like different variables. The version is stated to have desirable discriminant validity if every loading indicator price of a latent variable > 0.7 or has a rectangular root of AVE that is more than the correlation price among constructs of different latent variables (Ghozali, 2014:40). The effects of the discriminant validity take a look at are in Table 9

Table 9: Discriminant Validity Results

	<i>Employee Performance</i>	<i>Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior</i>	<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	<i>Workplace Environment</i>
Employee Performance	0.808			
Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior	0.517	1,000		
Job Satisfaction	0.628	0855	0.800	
Workplace Environment	0.668	0.821	0.798	0.799

From Table 9 it can be explained that from the results of the four variables having a loading indicator value, all variables have a value > 0.70, so it can be said that the data has good discriminant validity.

3. Composite Reliability, the assemble is accomplished through measuring Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. Constructs are declared dependable if the value of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability is above 0.7 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015: 76-77). The effects of the composite reliability check are in table 10.

Table 10: Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability Hasil results

Variable	cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability
Employee Performance	0.733	0.848
Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior	1,000	1,000
Job Satisfaction	0.728	0.841
Workplace Environment	0.857	0.898

Table 10 explains that every one of the variables on this examine have met Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability due to the fact their values are above the encouraged number, that is above 0. 7 which already meets the reliability criteria. Based on the general assessment results, each are convergent. discriminant validity, and composite reliability that have been defined above, it could be concluded that the signs as a degree of the latent variable are legitimate and dependable measures.

Inner Model Test

Testing of the inner model test is accomplished to peer the connection among variables, importance values, and R-square of the studies version. The structural version become evaluated the use of R-square for the structured variable t-test and the importance of the coefficients of the structural course parameters. Changes withinside the R-square value may be used to evaluate the impact of positive exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables which have a substantial impact.

Figure 2: Structural Model (Inner Model)

From Figure 2, it could be defined that the covariance of the indicator size is encouraged through the latent assemble or displays the version of the unidimensional assemble that is represented through an ellipse with numerous arrows from assemble to indicator. This version hypothesizes that adjustments in latent constructs have an effect on adjustments in indicators. In this version, there are exogenous variables, specifically statistics generation and competence, and endogenous variables, specifically task pleasure and worker performance. The evaluation of the version with PLS starts through searching on the R-square for every structured latent variable. Changes withinside the R-square value can be used to assess the effect of fine exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables that have a great effect. Table 11 suggests the R-square estimation outcomes the use of SmartPLS

Table 11: R-Square. Value

	<i>R Square</i>
<i>Employee Performance</i>	0.503
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	0.760

Table 11 indicates the R-square rate of the variable Employee Performance of 0.503 and the variable Job Satisfaction of 0.760. The higher the R-square rate, the extra the capability of the exogenous variable to be described with the resource of the use of the endogenous variable simply so the better the structural equation (Ghozali, 2014:42)

In addition to the use of R-square, the goodness of fit model is likewise measured the use of Q-Square predictive relevance for structural models, measuring how nicely the located values are generated via way of means of the version and additionally the expected parameters. Q2 charges greater than 0 suggest the release has predictive relevance, while it is much less than 0 suggests that the version no longer has any predictive relevance (Ghozali & Latan, 2015: 79) The q-Square calculation is accomplished by the formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q2 &= 1 - (1 - R1^2)(1 - R22) \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0.503^2)(1 - 0.7602) \\
 &= 1 - (0.747)(0.422) \\
 &= 0.685
 \end{aligned}$$

The effects of the Q Square Predictive Relevance (Q2) calculation show a value of 0.685, this means that the model suggests correct observations, wherein 68.5% of the connection among variables may be defined via way of means of the version, even as the rest (31.5%) is an error component or several things that are not covered in the Research Model. The assessment of the inner model that's measured primarily based totally on Q Square Predictive Relevance (Q2) and Goodness of Fit (GoF) above suggests that the version shaped via way of means of the constructs has a superb model category.

Hypothesis test

Hypothesis checking out is completed through t-statistics through finding out for checking out direct and oblique outcomes or checking out mediating variables. In the subsequent sections, the consequences of the direct have an impact on take a look at and the mediating variable take a look at are defined respectively.

Direct Effect Test

The importance of the envisioned parameters offers very beneficial statistics approximately the connection among the studies variables. The basis utilized in testing the hypothesis is the value contained withinside the output end result for inner weight. Table 12 provides the expected results for testing the structural model

Table 12: Direct Effect Test Results

No	Relationship between Variables	Coefficient Track	P Values	Information
1	<i>Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior -> Employee Performance</i>	0.386	0.027	Significant
2	<i>Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior -> Job Satisfaction</i>	0.613	0.000	Significant
3	<i>Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance</i>	0.474	0.003	Significant
4	<i>Workplace Environment -> Employee Performance</i>	0.607	0.000	Significant
5	<i>Workplace Environment -> Job Satisfaction</i>	0.295	0.012	Significant

The outcomes of testing the studies hypothesis primarily based totally on Table 12 are as follows:

- 1) Hypothesis Testing 1: There is a positive impact among Employee' Environmentally-Friendly to Employee Performance. This end result may be visible withinside the route coefficient value of 0.386 with a p-value of 0.027. The p-value is much less than 0.05 (alpha 5%). Based on this, hypothesis 1 is said accepted.
- 2) Hypothesis Testing 2: There is a positive impact among employees' Environmentally-Friendly to Job Satisfaction. This end result may be visible withinside the route coefficient value of 0.613 with a p-value of 0.000. The p-value is much less than 0.05 (alpha 5%). Based on this, hypothesis 2 is said accepted.
- 3) Hypothesis Testing 3: There is a positive impact among Job Satisfaction to Employee Performance. This end result may be visible withinside the route coefficient value of 0.474 with a p-value of 0.003. The p-value is much less than 0.05 (alpha 5%). Based on this, hypothesis 3 is said accepted.
- 4) Hypothesis Testing 4: There is a positive impact on Workplace Environment to Employee Performance. This end result may be visible withinside the route coefficient value of 0.607 with a p-value of 0.000. The p-value is much less than 0.05 (alpha 5%). Based on this, hypothesis 4 is said accepted.
- 5) Hypothesis Testing 5: There is a positive impact on Workplace Environment to Job Satisfaction. This end result may be visible withinside the route coefficient value of 0.295 with a p-value of 0.012. The p-value is much less than 0.05 (alpha five%). Based on this, hypothesis 5 is said accepted.

Based at the consequences of checks done the use of the SmartPLS 3.2.8 application, the following research model image can be presented:

Figure 3: Full Structural Model(PLS Bootstrapping)

Indirect Effects Test Through Mediation Variables

The importance of the expected parameters gives very beneficial records approximately the connection among the studies variables. The basis used to test the hypothesis is the value contained in the output result for the internal weight. Table 13 provides the estimated output for partial model testing.

Table 13: Test result Indirect Influence

No	Variable Mediation	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	Note:
1	Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.093 (N.Sig)	0.525 (Sig)	0.613 (Sig)	0.474 (Sig)	full Mediated
2	Workplace Environment -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.454 (Sig)	0.677 (Sig)	0.295 (Sig)	0.474 (Sig)	Partially Mediated

The results of the verification of the indirect impact by the mediation variable based mainly on the total table 13 are as follows:

1) Job Satisfactionable to mediate the indirect have an impact on of Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior on Employee Performance. This final result is demonstrated by the mediation test carried out, it seems that the impact c and the impact d have a good dimensional value while the impact a is not good.. The outcomes of this check decide Employee Environmentally-Friendly Behavior can have an effect on Employee Performance via Job Satisfaction may be demonstrated empirically. Based on those outcomes, it is able to be interpreted that the better the Job Satisfaction and supported Environmentally-Friendly Behavior, so Employee Performance will increase. Other stats likely to be reported, variable mediating impact Oblique job satisfaction impacts eco-friendly behavior for individual employee performance Fully mediated. This localization is a sign that the Environmentally Friendly Behavior variable cannot do this seriously impact on the employee performance variable without leaving aside the job satisfaction variable.

2) Job Satisfaction can mediate indirect have an impact on on Workplace Environment to Employee Performance. This end result is proven from the mediation check conducted, it seems that impact c, impact d, and impact a have good sized values. The outcomes of this test decide Workplace Environment can have an effect on Employee Performance via Job Satisfaction may be demonstrated empirically. Based on those outcomes, it is able to be interpreted that the better the Job Satisfaction and supported Workplace Environment, so Employee Performance will increase. Other statistics that may be conveyed, variable mediating impact Job Satisfactionon oblique have an impact on Workplace Environment to Employee Performance individual Partially Mediated. This locating is a sign that the variable Workplace Environment can considerably have an impact on the variable Employee Performance with out going via the variable Job Satisfaction

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of testing the direct and indirect effects, it can be concluded that in testing the direct effect, all proposed hypotheses can be accepted, namely, there is a positive influence between Employee' Environmentally-Friendly on Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction, there is a positive influence between Job Satisfaction to Employee Performance and There is a positive influence between Workplace Environment to Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction.

Based on the results of data analysis from this study, it can be answered from research questions that Employee' Environmentally-Friendly and Workplace Environment significantly affect Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction,

This study also tested media or indirect effects which resulted in the conclusion that Job Satisfactionable mediates the indirect influence of Employee' Environmentally-Friendly Behavior on Employee Performance. Besides that, Job Satisfactionable mediates indirect influence on Workplace Environment to Employee Performance.

Suggestions and Further Research

Based at the outcomes of this study, it could be visible that the significance of Employee' Environmentally-Friendly and Workplace Environment in an employer as it considerably impacts Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction, so it's miles recommended that employees can enhance their overall performance and sense task satisfaction, each of those elements have to obtain interest from the employer's management.

For further research, it is suggested to be able to develop variables by adding several related variables, besides that research can be carried out in several organizations with a wider sample

REFERENCES

- [1] Abdulghaffar, Nadia, 2017, Green Workplace Behavior in Saudi Arabia: The Case of EnviroCO, Journal of Management and Sustainability; Vol. 7, No. 1; 2017
- [2] Aiken, LH, Clarke, SP, Sloane, DM, Sochalski, JA, Busse, R., Clarke, H., et al. (2001). Nurses' reports on hospital care in five countries. Health Affairs, 20(3), 43-53
- [3] Ajala, EM, (2012), The Influence of Workplace environment on Workers' Welfare, Performance and Productivity, The African Symposium: Journal of the African Educational Research Network Volume 12 issue 1 pp; 141-149

- [4] Al-Anzi, NM (2009). Workplace environment and its impact on employees'performance. A study submitted to Project Management Department in Saudi Aramco, Open University of Malaysia
- [5] Al-Omari, Khaled and Okasheh, Haneen, 2017, The Influence of Work Environment on Job Performance: A Case Study of Engineering Company in Jordan, International Journal of Applied Engineering Research ISSN 0973-4562 Volume 12, Number 24, pp; 15544-15550
- [6] Anna Kane, 2011, Green recruitment, development and engagement, The British Psychological Society INF183 03/2011 pp; 6 - 17
- [7] Armstrong, M. (2006). Strategic Human Resource Management: A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice, 10th ed. London: Kogan Page.
- [8] Badayai, AR (2012). A Theoretical Framework and Analytical Discussion on Uncongenial Physical Workplace Environment and Job Performance [22] among Workers in Industrial Sectors. Social and Behavioral Sciences, 42, 486-495.
- [9] Breau, M., & Rhéaume, A., 2014, The relationship between empowerment and work environment on job satisfaction, intent to leave, and quality of care among ICU nurses. Dynamics, 25(3), 16-24.
- [10] Cascio, Wayne F, 2000, Managing a Virtual Workplace, Academy of Management Executive, Vol. 14, No. 3, 2000, pp; 81-90
- [11] Chandrasekar, K., 2011, Workplace environment and its impact on organizational performance in public sector organizations. International journal of enterprise computing and business systems, 1(1), 1-19.
- [12] Daily, BF, Bishop, JW, & Govindarajulu, N. (2009). Conceptual model for organizational citizenship behavior directed toward the environment. Business & Society, 48, 243-256.
- [13] De Giovanni, P. 2012, Do internal and external environmental management contribute to the triple bottom line? int. J. Opera. prod. Manag. 32, pp; 265–290.
- [14] El-Zeiny, RMA (2013), Interior Design of Workplace and Performance Relationship: Private Sector Corporations in Egypt, Asian Journal of Environment-Behavior Studies, Vol. 4, No. 11
- [15] Frese, M., & Sonnentag, S. (2000). High performance: An action theory approach. Working Papers. University of Giessen and University of Konstanz
- [16] Hadizadeh Talasaz, Z., Nourani Saadoldin, S., & Taghi Shakeri, M., 2014, The relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among midwives working in healthcare centers of Mashhad, Iran. Journal of Midwifery and Reproductive Health, 2 (3), pp; 157-164.
- [17] Hameed, Amina & Amjad, Shela. (2009). Impact of office design on employees' Productivity: A case study of Banking Organizations of Abbottabad, Pakistan. Journal Of Public Affairs, Administration and Management, 3(1), 2009.
- [18] Heath, B. (2006). Effect of perceived work environment on employee's job behavior and organizational effectiveness, Journal of Applied Psychology Banarashindu, University, Varanasi.
- [19] Jamil, M., (2016). Job Rotation and Employee Performance: The Role of Job Satisfaction and Variation in Job Skills as Intervening Variables. Journal of Economics Management and Secretarial. Vol. 1, No. 2.
- [20] Kasim, N., Adolfina., & Hendra N. Tawas., (2017). Analysis of training, work placement, and employee transfer and their effect on employee job satisfaction for non-medical employees at Prof Dr. RSUP. R.D Kandou Manado. EMBA Journal, Vol. 5, No. 2.
- [21] Kazemian A, Nooriyan K, Parvin K., 2005, Survey the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance of nurses in Chahar Mahal Bakhtiari. Journal of nursing and midwifery of Gilan.2005; 15(54): 39_44
- [22] Kwak, H., Anderson, RE, Leigh, TW, & Bonifield, SD (2019). Impact of salesperson macro-adaptive selling strategy on job performance and satisfaction. Journal of Business Research, 94, 42-55.

- [23] Lee, YS, & Brand, JL, 2005, Effects of control over office workspace on perceptions of the work environment and work outcomes. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 25, 323 – 333.
- [24] Luthans, F., Norman, SM Avoli, BJ and Avey, JB, 2008, The Mediating Role of Psychological Capital in the Supportive Organizational Climate-Employee Performance Relationship, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Zero. 29, No. 2, pp; 219 – 238
- [25] Maulana Usop A, Askandar K, Langguyuan-Kadtong M, Onotan Usop DAS., 2013, Work performance and job satisfaction among teachers. *International Journal of Humanities and social sciences*. 2013; 3(5) pp: 245_252
- [26] Mirmolae T, Dargahi H, Kazemnezhad A, Mohajerrahbari M., 2005, Job Satisfaction of Midwives. *Hayat Journal*. 2005; 11(24,25) pp: 87_95
- [27] Moazen Z, Movahedmohamadi H, Rezvanfar A, Mirtorabi M., 2011, Evaluation factors that affect job performance of Agriculture educators in Tehran schools, *Journal of new approach in Educational Management*, 2011, 1 (5), pp: 115-134
- [28] Mohammad, Z. (2017). The effect of organizational culture and working environment on employee performance; study of the example of printing company. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 72(12).
- [29] Monjamed Z, Ghorbani T, Mostofian F, Oveysipoor R, Nakhostpandi S, Mahmoodi M., 2004, Job satisfaction of nursing working in health centers. *Hayat Journal*. 2004; 10(23): 39-48.
- [30] Nadia Abdulghaffar, 2017, Green Workplace Behavior in Saudi Arabia: The Case of EnviroCO, *Journal of Management and Sustainability*; Vol. 7, No. 1; 2017
- [31] Nanzushi Cynthia, 2015, The Effect Of Workplace Environment of Employee Performance in the Mobile Telecommunication Firms in Nairobi City County, Research Project, Master of Business Administration, University of Nairobi
- [32] Ni Kadek Suryani, Made Wardana, Desak Ketut Sintaasih, and Ida Bagus Ketut Surya, 2017, Human Resources Management Practice and Organizational Performance (case study of Line Manager Support in Star-Hotel Bali Indonesia), *International Business Management* 11 (7), 1523 -1531, 2017
- [33] Ni Kadek Suryani, Kadek Dewi Indah Laksemimi and Mateus Ximenes. 2019. *Organizational Behavior Textbook*, Nilacakra Publisher, Denpasar Bali
- [34] Ramli, Abdul Haeba, 2019, Work Environment, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in Health Services, *Business and Entrepreneurial Review*, Vo. 19, Bo. 1, April 2019, pp; 29 – 42
- [35] Robertson, JL, & Barling, J. (2013). Greening organizations through leaders' influence on employees' pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 34, 176-194.
- [36] Samani, SA, Rasid, SZA, & Sofian, SB (2015). Perceived level of personal control over the work environment and employee satisfaction and work performance. *Performance Improvement*, 54(9), 28-35.
- [37] Samson, Gitahi Njenga, Waiganjo, Maina & Koima, Joel, (2015), Effect of Workplace Environment on the Performance of Commercial Banks Employee in Nakuru Town, *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*, Volume 3, Issue 12, December 2015, pp ; 76-89
- [38] Sedarmayanti. (2003). *Working Procedures and Work Productivity an Overview of Aspects of Ergonomics or the link between Man and Work Environment*. Bandung: Forward Mandar.
- [39] Shikdar, A. & Shawaqed, NM, ((2003), Worker Productivity, and Occupational Health And Safety Issues in Selected Industries, *Journal of Computers & Industrial Engineering* Volume 45 (2003) 563–572, Elsevier
- [40] Smith, Marilyn Farmer and Wendy Yellowley, 2013, *Organization Behavior* 1st Edition, eBook Published 5 March 2013, London Pub, Routledge
- [41] Srivastava, AK, 2008, Effect of Perceived Work Environment on Employees Job Behavior and Organizational Effectiveness, *Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, January 2008, Vol. 34, No.1, 47-55

- [42] Steg, L., & Vlek, CAJ (2009). Encouraging pro-environmental behavior: an integrative review and research agenda. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 29, 309-317
- [43] Stup, R. (2003). Control the factors that influence employee success. *Managing the Hispanic Workforce Conference*. Cornell University and Pennsylvania State University.
- [44] Uğur Yozgat, Serra Yurtkoru, Elif Bilginoglu, 2013, Job stress and job performance among employees in the public sector in Istanbul: examining the moderating role of emotional intelligence, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 75 (2013) pp; 518 – 524
- [45] Wang, N. and Boubekri, M. (2010), “Investigation of declared seating preference and measured cognitive performance in a sunlit room”, *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 226–238.
- [46] Westerman, JW, & Yamamura, JH (2007). Generational preferences for work environment fit: Effects on employee outcomes. *Career Development International*.
- [47] Yperen NWV., 2003, On the Link Between Different Combinations of Negative Affectivity (NA) and Positive Affectivity (PA) and job Performance, *Personality and Individual Differences Journal*, 2003; 35:1873–1881.